

International Journal of Advance Research Publication and Reviews

Vol 03, Issue 6, pp 314-320, June, 2026

The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Consumers' Social Identity

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.55248/gengpi.07.0626.15a45>

ABSTRACT :

Consumer trust and loyalty are some of the most critical aspects to target when it comes to marketing. In this modern time, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has become an essential strategy in building these aspects, particularly as ethical, social, and environmental concerns continuously influence consumer behaviour. In this study, the researchers explore the influence of CSR on consumers' social identity, particularly in the local setting of Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. It focuses on the three core pillars of CSR, specifically the People, Planet, and Profit, based on the Triple Bottom Line Theory (Elkington, 1998) and Social Identity Theory (Tajfel and Turner, 1979). It examines five dimensions of social identity: attitude, self-identity expression, social-identity expression, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control.

Data were collected using a descriptive-quantitative approach. The researchers gathered data from 217 consumers selected through convenience sampling. A researcher-made Likert-scale questionnaire assessed perceptions of CSR practices and their relationship with consumer identity. In order to determine the significance and strength of correlation, Spearman's rho correlation was applied. The findings from this study showed a statistically significant positive correlation between CSR and all dimensions of social identity ($p < 0.001$). The Planet dimension gained the strongest consumer agreement, which indicates that consumers have high awareness and support for CSR initiatives that are environmentally sustainable. On the other hand, the People dimension gained lower agreement, specifically when the respondents were asked about their willingness to pay premium prices for socially responsible products and services.

These findings suggest that CSR initiatives focusing on environmental efforts have a significant influence on consumers' social identity. Meanwhile, there is a strong need for improved communication and community engagement, as emphasised by the relatively weaker influence of the People dimension, consisting of social initiatives, on consumers' social identity. Increased efforts in improving communication and engagement can further strengthen the correlation between CSR and consumer values, which can also strengthen brand relationships, drive customer loyalty, and build a more meaningful and impactful psychological and social identification with ethically responsible businesses.

1. Introduction

The world is currently facing severe environmental crises such as global warming and climate change due to industrialization. These crises have harmful effects on the life of humankind and of the entire Planet. Aside from environmental concerns, there are also social issues persisting in many industries, such as worker exploitation, unfair wages, and unequal distribution of employment opportunities. In the face of increasingly alarming global challenges, the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has appeared as a vital framework. CSR is an initiative that represents a self-regulating business model wherein companies assume themselves to be accountable for their societal, environmental, and economic impact. CSR practices enable companies to function beyond traditional corporate motives by actively contributing to society and the environment through reducing carbon footprints, promoting renewable energy, and participating in social initiatives like community development, ethical labor practices, and consumer protection. By integrating CSR into their operations, businesses can foster trust among consumers, strengthen their brand reputation, and cultivate loyalty, all while benefiting society and the environment (Carroll & Shabana, 2019).

Current studies highlight the increasing significance of CSR in shaping consumer intentions, particularly regarding purchase decisions. Consumers today are increasingly perceptive, often considering a company's ethical conventions and social contributions when making purchasing decisions. Positive CSR efforts — such as promoting

environmental Sustainability or supporting social causes—can significantly enhance brand perception, increase consumer trust, and build long-term loyalty (Bhattacharya et al., 2020). Conversely, negative perceptions regarding a company's CSR efforts, such as involvement in unethical business practices or environmental irresponsibility, may result in consumer backlash and diminished brand loyalty (Suki, 2021).

Despite the expanding body of literature on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and its influence on consumer behaviour, there remains a research gap in understanding how CSR initiatives influence consumers' social identity, particularly in local contexts. Social identity—which includes attitude, self-identity expression, social identity expression, subjective norms, and behavioural control—plays a crucial role in shaping consumer attitudes and behaviours (Haslam et al., 2021).

This study differs from other literature because CSR is often evaluated in terms of its influence on purchase intentions. On the other hand, in this study, the impact of CSR on consumers' social identity is being explored.

According to Lee & Cho (2020) and Zhang & Dong (2023), brand perceptions and consumer loyalty are now highly influenced by CSR; thus, having a profound understanding on how it specifically influences consumers' social identity provides practical ideas for businesses and marketers to better align their CSR initiatives with values and norms accepted in the community to drive sustainable consumption.

The findings from this study are expected to guide businesses and marketers in formulating their CSR strategies to move beyond meeting ethical commitments and also uphold meaningful identity connections with consumers, particularly in regional areas like Cabiao, Nueva Ecija.

2. Research Method

2.1 Research Design

A descriptive-survey research method was used in this study entitled "The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Consumers' Social Identity." Best and Kahn (2020) stated that descriptive research is best used to represent aspects of a distinct population, condition, or phenomenon in an objective and organized manner. It aims to provide a detailed understanding of variables as they intrinsically happen without manipulation or power, making it well-suited for exploring the existing perceptions and attitudes of consumers toward Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and its impact on their social identity.

2.2 Participants

This research consists of a total of 217 respondents, who are consumers and are residents of Cabiao, Nueva Ecija, all of legal age. There are both male and female respondents, which allows for the representation of a diverse segment of the population who also engage actively in the local marketplace. Since this study explores the influence of CSR on consumers' social identity, particularly in regional areas like Cabiao, the chosen respondents are suitable for the accomplishment of this study's objective because they have direct interactions with the CSR initiatives of companies and businesses in their local area, and they can also directly respond to them. Their perspectives can be valuable for understanding how CSR resonates with people belonging to various groups within their society. It holds a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error, which provides a statistically adequate representation of the target population. Convenience sampling was the sampling technique utilized. It is a non-probability sampling method wherein accessibility and willingness to participate are the factors used for selecting the respondents. It is also a widely used sampling technique in terms of applied research, especially when there is inadequate time, resources, or accessibility to the entire population frame. It allows for faster data collection and is vital for exploratory studies. However, according to Scribbr (2023), it is essential to keep in mind that this type of sampling technique may introduce sampling bias, which has the potential to affect the generalizability of the results to a broader population.

2.3 Instrumentation

The researchers used a researcher-made questionnaire to gather relevant data for exploring the influence of CSR on consumers' social identity. This instrument was meticulously constructed to assess the respondents' level of agreement on CSR and its influence on their social identity. The questionnaire is divided into two Principal parts, comprising a total of ninety-two (92) items, and employs a five-point Likert scale format for responses. The researchers provide complete instructions before the questions to allow the respondents to answer with clarity and consistency. The provided instructions also remind the respondents to choose the option that sincerely reflects their perceptions and experiences as consumers.

2.4 Validation of Instrument

The questionnaire was evaluated and validated by a panel of three professionals with expertise in business research, marketing, and corporate social responsibility to ensure accuracy and validity in terms of applicability, transparency, and association with research objectives. Relevant revisions were then made to enhance the quality and accuracy of the items based on the validators' feedback and suggestions. The instrument validation allowed the researchers to ensure that reliable data would be gathered to support the study's claim in exploring the influence of on consumers' social identity.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers started the data collection process by formally asking for the approval of the target population, and upon confirming their approval, the researchers gave them the instrument through face-to-face or online via Google Forms, based on whatever process would maximize accessibility and convenience. The researchers used a convenience sampling technique to select the respondents who were accessible, gathering 217 respondents in the vicinity of Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. Clear instructions were provided to guide them while answering the questionnaires. The entire data collection process lasted for seven (7) days.

2.6 Analysis of Data

The information gathered in this study was arranged and used the research design as a guide. The researchers employed the Mean to determine the respondents' level of agreement regarding CSR practices under the three dimensions of People, Planet, and Profit, as well as the influence of CSR on social identity. Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient was used to assess the strength and direction of the relationship between CSR practices and consumers' social identity. **The Likert Scale was utilized as an instrument for interpreting levels of agreement in the questionnaire.**

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter included a thorough presentation and discussion of the data analysis and findings from 217 respondents. The survey's data were provided in tabular form with supporting interpretations, conclusions, and theoretical underpinnings

Table 1
Respondents' Level Agreement on Corporate Social Responsibility

Respondents' Level of Agreement on Corporate Social Responsibility	WM	VI
People	4.16	Agree
Planet	4.25	Strongly Agree

Profit	4.23	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.21	Strongly Agree

Legend: 5 – Strongly Agree; 5.00 - 4.21– Agree; 4.20 - 3.41– Somewhat Agree; 3.40 - 2.61– Disagree; 2.60 – 1.81 – Strongly Disagree; 1.80 – 1.00

Table 1 presents the respondents' level of agreement on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), with an overall weighted mean of 4.21 and the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." The respondents' level of agreement on CSR, in terms of Planet with a weighted mean of 4.25 and the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree," Profit with a weighted mean of 4.23 and the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree," and People with a weighted mean of 4.16 and the verbal interpretation of "Agree."

Table 2
Respondents' Level of Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Consumers' Social Identity

Respondents' Level of Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Consumers' Social Identity	WM	VI
Attitudes	4.32	Strongly Agree
Self-identity Expression	4.05	Agree
Social-identity Expression	3.83	Agree
Subjective Norms	3.74	Agree
Behavioral Control	4.17	Agree
Overall	4.02	Agree

Legend: 5 – Strongly Agree; 5.00 - 4.21– Agree; 4.20 - 3.41– Somewhat Agree; 3.40 - 2.61– Disagree; 2.60 – 1.81 – Strongly Disagree; 1.80 – 1.00'

Table 2 presents the respondents' level of agreement on how Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) influences consumers' social identity, with an overall weighted mean of 4.02 and the verbal interpretation of "Agree." In terms of specific dimensions, Attitudes had a weighted mean of 4.32 with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree," Behavioral Control had a weighted mean of 4.17 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree," Self-identity Expression had a weighted mean of 4.05 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree," Social-identity Expression had a weighted mean of 3.83 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree," and Subjective Norms had a weighted mean of 3.74 with a verbal interpretation of "Agree."

Table 3
Significant Correlation Between Corporate Social Responsibility and Consumers' Social Identity

INDICATORS	P-VALUE	DECISION	CONCLUSION
Attitude	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Self-identity Expression	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Social-Identity Expression	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Subjective Norm	0.002	Reject Ho	Significant
Behavioral Control	0.003		
Overall	0.0016	Reject Ho	Significant

Legend: Accept Ho if computed $\chi^2 > \chi^2_{0.05}$ = Not Significant; Reject Ho if computed $\chi^2 \leq \chi^2_{0.05}$ = Significant

Table 3 presents the significant correlation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and consumers' social identity, yielding an overall p-value of 0.0016. The results indicate that the p-values of attitude (<.001), self-identity expression (<.001), social-identity expression (<.001), subjective norm (0.002), and behavioral control (0.003) are all less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho) was rejected, and the relationship between corporate social responsibility and consumers' social identity was found to be significant.

4. Conclusion

The following conclusions are derived from the findings above:

- 4.1. The respondents demonstrated a high level of agreement with the verbal interpretation of "strongly agree" on Corporate Social Responsibility across all three dimensions: People, Planet, and Profit..
- 4.2. The respondents agree that Corporate Social Responsibility influences consumers' social identity in terms of attitude, self-identity expression, social identity expression, subjective norms, and behavioral control.
- 4.3. The researchers rejected the null hypothesis and therefore there was a significant correlation between the food service attributes and consumer buying behavior.

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, we, the researchers, give our deepest and sincerest thanks to Almighty God for granting us the strength, wisdom, and perseverance to complete this research study. His divine guidance and countless blessings made this endeavor possible. We are profoundly grateful to our research adviser, Mr. Richard V. Gonzales, for his unwavering guidance throughout the entire research process. His support—from the initial discussions of the title to the end, his patience and understanding, greatly motivated us to complete this study. To the panelists, Engr. Fernando F. Estingor, Dr. Jenny Q. Estingor, Mr. Rogene C. Esguerra, Mr. Jomar E. Pineda and Ms. May M. Galang, for their continuous support, valuable insights, and expert guidance throughout the development of our study. Their encouragement has been instrumental in shaping the direction and quality of our work.

We would also like to extend our appreciation to the Polytechnic University of the Philippines Cabiao Campus, including the faculty members and staff, for providing us with the knowledge, tools, and support necessary to accomplish this research.

To our families and friends, thank you for your endless patience, love, and moral support. Your presence and encouragement have been a source of motivation throughout this journey.

Finally, we are sincerely thankful to all the respondents who willingly shared their time and input. Your cooperation played a crucial role in the success of our research.

To everyone who has been part of this academic journey—directly or indirectly—our heartfelt thanks.

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